

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: IKEE****FIRST NAME: ROBERT****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. Which of the following is the key element of a strong essay structure?

- Strong introduction with a hook and background information
- Body paragraphs
- A catchy title
- Clear thesis statement that outlines the main argument of the essay.¹**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Course pack: Period 1*. 4th ed. (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

2. Which of the following resources is recommended in the ACA 401D Course pack (specifically for doctoral students)?

- A Manual for Writers of Term Papers, Theses, and Dissertations (Turabian) ²**
- Write Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking and Learning (Sebranek)
- A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition) by James.
- English Style Guide of the European Commission Directorate-General for Translation

3. Which of the following is the most important aspect for a strong research paper according to Turabian?

- Fancy vocabulary
- A well-defined research questions³**
- Colorful fonts and margins
- A large number of references

² Ibid., 44.

³Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. 9th ed. (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 134.

4. Turabian acknowledges that the way students conduct research has changed. What does she say has remained constant throughout these changes?

- The need for handwritten notes
- The importance of a strong problem statement⁴**
- The use of rotary phones for citations
- Reliance on encyclopedias as the primary source

5. According to the Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research (Second Edition), what is the primary benefit of collaboration among researchers?

- Increased competition for funding opportunities
- Sharing expertise and diverse perspectives⁵**
- Reducing the workload for each individual researcher
- Limiting the overall cost of the research project

⁴ Ibid., 134.

⁵ James P. Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, College of Education, 2017), 478.

6. When developing your research proposal, you can use the following strategies to avoid plagiarism.

- Direct quotes enclosed in quotation marks; summarizing and paraphrasing while still conveying the original meaning, and citing the source⁶**
- Copying and pasting large sections of text from your sources without proper citation.
- Using a thesaurus to find synonyms for words in your sources.
- Asking your friend to proofread your proposal for grammar errors.

7. The research methodology a researcher choose should influence the data collection methods he employs. Which of the following methods would be most appropriate for a case study?

- Large-scale survey
- In-depth interviews with key participants⁷:**
- Content analysis of historical documents
- Experimentation with a control group

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. (New York: Columbia University Press, 2018), 223-224.

⁷ Ibid., 464.

8. When selecting a qualitative research methodology, it is important to consider the philosophical underpinnings that align with your research goals. Which of the following best describes the philosophical perspective of social constructivism/interpretivism?

- Knowledge is a fixed and objective reality.
- Social realities are constructed through shared meanings and experiences.⁸**
- Researcher's own background and biases have on the research process
- The researcher can achieve complete objectivity in their research.

9. According to the English Style Guide, which of the following punctuation marks is generally preferred to separate two independent clauses?

- Semicolon (;)
- Colon (:)
- Comma (,)⁹**
- Period (.)

⁸ Ibid., 223-224.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A handbook for authors and translators in the European Commission* (Brussels: European Commission, 2021), 31.

10. In the English Style Guide, clarity and conciseness are emphasized throughout. Which of the following best reflects this principle?

- Using complex sentence structures with multiple clauses.
- Favoring active voice over passive voice for a more direct style.**¹⁰
- Including lengthy background information in the main point.
- Including unnecessary jargon and technical terms for a more professional tone.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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¹⁰ Ibid., 17.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.